

Automated Detection of Missing Links in Developed Bicycle Networks

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Summary

Cycling is an effective solution for making urban transport more sustainable. However, bicycle networks are typically developed in a slow, piecewise process that leaves open numerous gaps. Here, we develop the IPCC procedure (Identify, Prioritize, Cluster, Classify) for finding the most important missing links in developed urban bicycle networks, by analyzing street networks from OpenStreetMap. We apply the IPCC procedure to Copenhagen, report the 105 priority gaps and find considerable overlaps with the city's Cycle Path Prioritization Plan. Our results show how network analysis of open source GIS data can serve as support tool for bicycle network planning.

KEYWORDS: network analysis, bicycle network, urban data science, OpenStreetMap

1. Introduction: Towards a sustainable mobility system

In the face of increasing urbanization (UN, 2018) and of transport being one of the most problematic sectors in terms of emission reductions (Lamb et al., 2021), urban transportation systems play a decisive role in tackling the climate crisis. There is enormous potential to be harnessed by 'greening' the transportation sector through a modal shift towards active and more sustainable mobility modes, such as cycling, both in terms of climate change mitigation and socioeconomic benefits (High-level Advisory Group on Sustainable Transport, 2016; Gössling, 2019). In practice, however, bicycle infrastructure development is often impeded by a particularly pervasive political inertia due to the complex interdependencies of car-centrism (Feddes et al., 2020; Mattioli et al., 2020).

2. Motivation: A framework for data-driven bicycle network planning

A rigorously structured, data-driven, systemic approach to bicycle network planning is a necessary precondition for an evidence-based transformation of the mobility sector. As of today, urban bicycle planning practices are characterized by a variety of context-specific, incremental approaches which are difficult to extrapolate to other locations (Larsen et al., 2013; Milakis and Athanasopoulos, 2014; Mitra et al., 2017; Skov-Petersen et al., 2017). Setting up a robust framework for bicycle network planning would enable cities to take coordinated efforts for a sustainable transition of urban mobility and support them in their strategic planning and decision-making. Such a framework would allow for a holistic approach towards the transportation system, accounting for multimodal mobility and for environmental and socio-economic benefits together with equity implications. This study aims at contributing to a computational foundation of bicycle network planning by tackling the following question: *How can the detection of missing links in developed bicycle networks be automated, using open source GIS data?*

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3. Results: A tool with minimum data requirements to identify missing links in bicycle networks

A cyclist on their way through a well-connected, developed bicycle network like in Copenhagen will often find themselves suddenly having to share the road with cars for a while, or having to cross unprotected intersections with a high traffic load. Here we formalize this intuitive concept of a 'missing link' in the bicycle network and develop an automated procedure to find the most important ones. We call our procedure *IPCC* after its four main steps: Identify, Prioritize, Cluster, Classify. The IPCC procedure is most applicable to cities that have an already well developed bicycle network. Our method is based only on topological network properties deduced from open source GIS data and thus has minimal data requirements.

To showcase the applicability of our approach, we used the IPCC procedure for the city of Copenhagen and obtained a list of 105 top priority gaps, as shown in Figure 1, belonging to five different classes. We identified the following gap classes: *Street*; *Intersection*; *Right-turn lane*; *Bridge*; *Roundabout*; and *Error*. Figure 2 shows the highest ranked gap for each of the gap classes. The classification scheme is meant to facilitate both the interpretation of results from bicycle network analysis and the decision-making within a subsequent planning process. Given that the classification was developed through manual inspection and on-site visits of the gaps identified in Copenhagen, it might need to be adapted or extended for other urban contexts in future research.

A comparison of our results with the city's most recent Cycle Path Prioritization Plan showed substantial overlaps, both with citizen input on missing bicycle network links and with the city's list of prioritized locations for the construction of new bicycle infrastructure. The IPCC procedure thus demonstrates how data-driven network analysis on a city-wide scale can meaningfully complement manual planning processes. We therefore consider this study a further crucial step towards a consolidation of computational methods for bicycle network analysis.

4. Reproducibility

Our overarching goal is to support data-driven bicycle network planning by providing efficient open source solutions to all potential stakeholders. The reproducibility and accessibility of results, as well as the possibility to flexibly refine the methods and the underlying code, are therefore key elements of this study. Both the code for the IPCC procedure and the OpenStreetMap data used as input for the Copenhagen case study are available on [GitHub](#). A detailed step-by-step description of the IPCC procedure, including algorithms, heuristics, and parameter tuning, is provided in Vybornoova et al. (2022). An interactive visualization of the results is available on [fixbike.net](#).

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Figure 1 Top 105 gaps in the bicycle network of Copenhagen, by class: streets in orange, intersections in yellow, bridges in red, right-turn lanes in pink, roundabouts in violet. Errors are not shown. Numbered blue circles indicate the top 5 gaps (see Figure 2 for detail plots). The street network is shown in grey, the bicycle network in black. See <http://fixbike.net> for an interactive version of this map.

Figure 2 The five bicycle network gap classes in Copenhagen. For each class, the highest ranked gap is shown. From left to right: Street gap (rank 4) on Jacob Erlandsens Gade; Intersection gap (rank 2) at the intersection of Øster Vøldgade/Grønningen; Right-turn lane gap (rank 6) at Nørre Allé/Øster Allé; Bridge gap (rank 1) on Knippelsbro; Roundabout gap (rank 41) at Sankt Kjelds Plads.

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Biographies

Anastassia Vybornova is a PhD fellow at the IT University of Copenhagen. Her research is centered around the consolidation of a computational, data-driven foundation for urban bicycle network analysis. Her preferred research methods are network science and data science with a transdisciplinary approach.

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